

SHAPE MEMORY BEHAVIOUR OF RE-ENTRANT UNIT CELL STRUCTURE BASED ON 3D PRINTED POLYURETHANE NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates shape memory characteristics, negative Poisson's ratio (NPR) and thermal stability of re-entrant (RE) structures made from polyurethane (PU)/halloysite nanotube (HNT) nanocomposites via fused deposition modelling (FDM). The addition of 10 wt% HNTs within PU matrices enhanced shape fixity ratio of PU/HNT nanocomposites by 12% despite a slight drop in both shape recovery ratio (9%) and NPR (60%), along with prolonged recovery time up to 45%. This result clearly indicated their promising commercial potential as a shape-memory shock absorber in the future. Furthermore, the incorporation of HNTs improved thermal stability of PU/HNT nanocomposites, which was shown by their relatively high thermal decomposition temperatures. It could be associated with barrier effect of HNTs to postpone the degradation of PU hard segments. Additionally, an entrapping mechanism of HNT lumens made a significant contribution in thermal stability improvement of 3D printed nanocomposite structures. Finally, the presence of HNTs also elevated glass transition temperature T_g , melting temperature T_m , crystallisation temperature T_c and the degree of crystallinity χ_c due to much better covalent bonding, microphase separation and nucleating effect of such nanoparticles in addition to mobility restriction of PU molecules.

1 INTRODUCTION

Re-entrant (RE) structures have drawn great attention due to their light-weight and high-strength characteristics, resulting in a high stiffness/strength to mass ratio. Besides, such desired structures also possess unique material behaviour, namely negative Poisson's ratio (NPR), which allows them to exhibit transverse expansion under uniaxial tension and transverse contraction when subjected to uniaxial compression [1]. Lakes [2] mentioned that RE structures with remarkable shear stiffness for the first time, motivated many researchers to create and develop various auxetic structures over many decades.

It is tedious work to manufacture RE structures using conventional manufacturing methods such as injection moulding and melt extrusion owing to their typical lattice structures constructed from simple unit cells with significantly high porosity [3]. This critical issue can be overcome with the aid of 3D printing technology to achieve free-form fabrication. When RE structures are made from shape-memory polyurethane (PU), resulting structures reveal great potential as shock absorbers in possession of shape memory behaviour, enabling them to recover after deformation by using external stimuli such as heat, light, electrical and magnetic fields. Nevertheless, PU possesses typical drawbacks associated with its

mechanical strength [4]. Therefore, such a material requires the reinforcements like fibres and nanoparticles. Among nanoparticles like carbon nanotubes (CNTs), montmorillonites (MMTs) and halloysite nanotubes (HNTs), HNTs have typical advantages since they are classified as a non-toxic material and become abundantly available in nature as low-cost additives to improve mechanical properties [5].

This study presents a comprehensive investigation with respect to the effect of different HNT content (i.e. 0, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 wt%) on shape memory behaviour of PU/HNT nanocomposites via fused deposition modelling (FDM). Besides, thermal stability of 3D printed RE structures was also evaluated. Initial nanocomposite samples were prepared via mixing and solution casting processes. They were then examined in compression and shape memory tests, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) to determine corresponding Poisson's ratio (PR), shape memory behaviour and thermal stability of 3D printed nanocomposites.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

Polyurethane (PU) MM 4520 [6] manufactured by SMP Technologies, Tokyo, Japan, was used as primary polymeric material in this study. Meanwhile, HNT particles were supplied by Imerys Ceramics Kaeo, New Zealand [7]. Dimethylformamide (DMF) [8] was employed as a chemical solvent to dissolve PU pellets for better HNT dispersion. DMF was supplied by Chem-Supply Pty Ltd., SA, Australia. The properties of PU and HNTs are listed in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Physical properties	Mechanical properties	Thermal properties
Melt viscosity (Pa·s at 215°C)	Young's modulus (MPa)	Glass transition temperature (°C)
3310	729	45
	Tensile strength at break (MPa)	
	41	
	Ultimate elongation (%)	
	600	
	Shore D hardness	
	72	

Table 1: PU MM-4520 properties [6].

Property	Value
Moisture content (%)	3.0
Specific gravity	2.55
pH (aqueous slurry at 20% solids)	3.5 – 4.5
Surface area [Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET)] (m ² /g)	25
Linear shrinkage (dried at 110°C) (%)	3.8
Modulus of rupture (dried at 110°C) (MPa)	2.9

Table 2: HNT properties [7].

To prepare nanocomposite samples, PU pellets and HNT particles were dried in a vacuum oven at 80°C for 4 and 8 h accordingly [6,9] in order to minimise adverse moisture effect, as depicted in Fig. 1. HNT particles were then dispersed in DMF with a mix ratio of 1:30 [10] using an ultrasonication bath at the frequency of 25 kHz, power intensity of 90% and sonication time of 1 h [11]. Meanwhile, PU pellets were dissolved in DMF (mix ratio: 1:8) [10]. Before mixing with PU pellets, DMF was heated in a magnetic stirrer at 300°C with the rotor speed of 700 rpm. At this temperature, PU pellets were gradually added into the beaker until such materials were fully dissolved to prevent sedimentation issue.

Afterwards, HNT/DMF mixture was added into PU/DMF under stirring and heating processes for approximately 30 min. PU/HNT/DMF mixture was then cast onto a glass container, and then heated again in an oven at 100°C for 24 h to remove the solvent. Finally, prepared nanocomposite films were stored in a desiccator containing silicon gels before further material testing and characterisation. It is worth mentioning that nanocomposite film preparation in this study followed the same procedure previously mentioned elsewhere [13, 14].

Figure 1: Flow chart of manufacturing PU/HNT nanocomposite films, filaments and samples [12].

The extrusion process was carried out using a single screw filament extruder, Filabot EX6 (Screw diameter: 16 mm and L/D ratio: 24), supplied by Filabot company, VT, USA. Such an extruder has four temperature chambers consisting of feed, back, middle and front zones with specific temperatures controlled at 45, 165, 165 and 165°C respectively. On the other hand, screw speed of filament extruder was set to 50 rpm to produce nanocomposite filaments.

Prior to an extrusion process, PU/HNT nanocomposite films were shredded and further chopped into small flakes with the thickness of 0.45 ± 0.1 mm, the width of 3.00 ± 0.1 mm and the length of 4.30 ± 0.5 mm. Processed flakes were then dried using a vacuum oven at a controlled temperature of 80°C for 4 h to reduce moisture content. After the extrusion process, nanocomposite filaments were spooled and further stored in airtight containers with silica gels in order to dry prepared filaments. Filament fabrication from virgin PU pellets also followed this procedure with the exception of no shredding and chopping. Processing parameters for filament extrusion are presented in Table 3.

Finally, nanocomposite samples were manufactured by employing a FDM printer Axiom 20 integrated with a built-in software APEX supplied by Airwolf 3D company, USA. The samples were created at various HNT contents according to Table 4. Meanwhile, the settings of selected 3D printing parameters and other fixed 3D printing parameters are listed in Tables 5 and 6.

Parameter	Setting
Front temperature (T_{front}) (°C)	165
Middle temperature (T_{mid}) (°C)	165
Back temperature (T_{back}) (°C)	165
Feed temperature (T_{feed}) (°C)	45
Extrusion speed (rpm)	50

Table 3: Settings of filament extrusion parameters.

Factor	Level					
	0	2	4	6	8	10
HNT content (wt%)						
Nozzle temperature (°C)	210			220		230
Print speed (mm/s)	10			20		30
Infill density (%)	40			70		100
Layer height (mm)	0.2			0.3		0.4

Table 4: Summary of different HNT contents and 3D printing parameters in this study.

Parameter	Setting
Nozzle temperature (°C)	210
Print speed (mm/s)	10
Infill density (%)	100
Layer height (mm)	0.4

Table 5: 3D printing parameter settings.

Parameter	Specific parameter	Setting
Quality	Shell thickness (mm)	1.6
	Initial layer thickness (mm)	0.5
	Initial layer line width (%)	120
	Top surface quality	precise
Fill	Bottom/top thickness (mm)	1.2
	Infill interface density	dense
	Infill type	triangle
	Infill overlap (%)	15
Temperature	Bed temperature (°C)	55
Speed	Travel speed (mm/s)	150
	Bottom layer speed (mm/s)	15
	Infill speed (mm/s)	30
Filament	Flow (%)	115
Retraction	Speed (mm/s)	30
	Distance (mm)	5
	Minimum travel (mm)	1.5
	Minimal extrusion before retracting (mm)	0.005

Table 6: Fixed 3D printing parameters for PU/HNT nanocomposites.

Compression tests at the first step were carried out to assess the influence of HNT content on Poisson's ratio (PR) of 3D printed samples. Re-entrant (RE) structures were employed in this study for compression tests, which were made from both neat PU and PU/HNT nanocomposites. RE structures, as illustrated in Fig 2(a), have the length of vertical strut (l) of 20 mm, the length of inclined strut (s) of 12 mm and the height (h) of 20 mm. On the other hand, the width (w), the cell thickness (t) and the angle of inclined strut (θ) of this structure are 20 mm, 2 mm and 40° accordingly. Compression tests were

performed with the load-cell capacity of 10 kN to conduct uniaxial quasi-static tests at room temperature in the in-plane y direction depicted in Fig. 2(b). Under the tests, RE structures were set on the fixed platen on the universal testing machine, and three structure samples were assessed for test reproducibility at each HNT content.

Figure 2: (a) A RE structure and its dimensions (in mm), (b) a schematic diagram of typical compression test for RE structure and (c) compression test for the investigation of shape memory behaviour of RE structure.

The crosshead speed of movable platen travelling downwards was set to 0.5 mm/min according to ASTM C365 standard. The test ended when a densification phenomenon was reached. Nominal stress σ and normal strain ε were determined based on equations (1) and (2) as follows

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{l \times w} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta h}{h} \quad (2)$$

where F and Δh are the applied load and the change of displacement between movable and fixed platens. The built-in software of the universal testing machine was used to automatically record such displacement along with time and force throughout compression tests.

PR in this study can be defined as the negative ratio of lateral strain to axial strain. The axial strain was calculated based on the platen displacement in the y -axis. On the other hand, a digital camera Fujifilm X-T3 manufactured by Fujifilm Corporation, Tokyo, Japan, was used to capture RE structure displacement in the x -axis. The resulting data were employed to determine the lateral displacement in the x -axis with the aid of DaVinci Resolve 18 and ImageJ 153 software. The values of axial strain ε and lateral strain ε_L were determined using equations (2) and (3). In addition, l and Δl denote initial length and the change of the length. Meanwhile, PR was calculated using equation (4) [15].

$$\varepsilon_L = \frac{\Delta l}{l} \quad (3)$$

$$PR = -\frac{\varepsilon_L}{\varepsilon} \quad (4)$$

Compression tests at the second test step to evaluate shape memory behaviour of RE structures were conducted at 50°C using an asphalt mixture performance tester (AMPT) with the load cell of 15 kN depicted in Fig. 2(c). This device is equipped with an oven, enabling it to perform compression at elevated temperatures. The compression process was ended immediately after Δh reached 8 mm where Δh of 5 mm was considered as the onset densification of RE structures. The oven employed at the first test step was also applied to evaluate shape memory behaviour of RE nanocomposite structures at the second test step. The oven heating temperature was set to 80°C for fast recovery and twisting effect.

Figure 3: Compression tests for shape memory behaviour of RE structures

Fig. 3 exhibits different heights of RE unit-cell samples, namely the height before compression h_o , the height after compression h_h , the height after load removal h_i and the height after recovery h_e . Equations (5)-(9) can be applied to determine shape fixity ratio R_f , shape recovery ratio R_r , the amount of deformation after load removal ε_u , maximum strain ε_m and the amount of reversible strain ε_p .

$$R_f = \frac{\varepsilon_u}{\varepsilon_m} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

$$R_r = \frac{\varepsilon_m - \varepsilon_p}{\varepsilon_m} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon_m = \frac{h_o - h_h}{h_o} \quad (7)$$

$$\varepsilon_u = \frac{h_o - h_i}{h_o} \quad (8)$$

$$\varepsilon_p = \frac{h_o - h_e}{h_o} \quad (9)$$

A thermogravimetric analyser (TGA) SDT 2960, supplied by TA Instruments, USA, was used to investigate thermal stability of neat PU and PU/HNT nanocomposites based on sample weight-loss method. A cooling system with cryofill liquid nitrogen was utilised to determine the weight loss of material samples. About 20 mg TGA samples were heated from 25 to 900°C with the heating rate of 10°C/min [13]. Conversely, a differential scanning calorimeter Discovery DSC 25, supplied by Texas Instruments, USA, was in operation to evaluate glass transition temperature (T_g), crystallisation temperature (T_c) and melting temperature (T_m) of neat PU and PU/HNT nanocomposites. About 4 mg DSC samples were placed in aluminium pans, then heated from -50 °C to 240°C with the heating rate of 20°C/min. To eradicate thermal history, an isothermal condition was kept at 240°C for 5 min. DSC samples were then cooled from 240°C to -50°C with the same cooling rate of 20°C/min again. Heating-cooling processes were replicated for the second time. T_g and T_m were then detected from the first heating while T_c was determined from the second heating.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of HNT Content on NPR

The addition of HNTs within PU matrices tended to restrict the mobility of polymeric chains, thus resulting in much higher stiffness. The presence of siloxane and aluminol groups on HNT surfaces

induced hydrogen bonding with PU molecular chains, which further reduced their mobility. Moreover, when HNT content was increased up to 10 wt%, it could reduce engineering strain specifically with respect to lateral strain. This is attributed to the limited effect on the movement of polymeric chains, thereby resulting in a decrease in NPR by approximately 60% (Fig. 4). RE structures made from PU/HNT nanocomposites had an auxetic behaviour due to their unique forms, which allowed them to encounter transverse contraction under uniaxial compression [16]. Once compression strain reached 10%, the curve section of the strut in the middle region of RE structure touched each other, which was followed by a decrease in lateral strain. It was evidently observed that all curves had a consistent trend from initial sharp rise to nearly the plateaus, which was in good agreement with Park et al. [17] to investigate the efficacy of chondrocyte proliferation for PU auxetic scaffolds in compressive tests, which was especially applicable to articular cartilage in tissue engineering. Overall, PR versus compressive strain curves of PU/HNT nanocomposites appeared to be in good accordance with Alomarah et al. [18] where PR values were calculated based on lateral engineering strain and axial engineering strain for RE structures under compressive loading in the x -direction.

Figure 4: Effect of HNT content on NPRs of PU and PU/HNT nanocomposite samples.

3.2 Effect of HNT content on shape memory behaviour

In relation to shape memory behaviour, the presence of HNTs induced three different effects on 3D printed nanocomposite samples. The first effect was associated with the improved ability of PU/HNT nanocomposite samples to be programmed, which enhanced their shape fixity ratio. The inclusion of 10 wt% HNTs could enhance the shape fixity ratio of nanocomposite samples up to 12%, as opposed to that of virgin PU according to Fig. 5(a). This phenomenon might be related to strain-induced crystallisation effect [17]. The incorporation of rigid nanofillers such as HNTs increased soft-segment crystallinity. Furthermore, the strain distribution in PU matrices in the vicinity of HNTs became greater under deformation. It could be induced by significant modulus difference between the matrices and the fillers [19]. Strain localisation promoted strain-induced crystallisation caused by higher crystallisation to limit the relaxation process of deformed polymeric chains. The increase of HNT content was detected to further enhance strain-induced crystallisation, as indicated by shorter h_i along with higher R_f .

The second effect was related to HNTs to prevent PU matrices from regaining their original form, leading to the reduction of shape recovery ratio. In particular, when PU was incorporated with 10 wt% HNTs, shape recovery ratio of resulting nanocomposite samples slightly declined to 9%. Final effect could be associated with the contribution of existing HNTs to hinder PU molecules from shape recovery, and further prolong the recovery time by 45% with the addition of 10 wt% HNTs in their nanocomposites according to Fig. 5(b).

Figure 5: (a) Shape fixity and shape recovery ratios and (b) recovery time of PU/HNT nanocomposites

3.3 Effect of HNT content on thermal stability

Thermal stability for PU/HNT nanocomposites was shown in their TGA thermograms in Fig. 6(a). Four decomposition temperatures, represented by T_{d1} , T_{d2} , T_{d3} and T_{d4} , were associated with hard segment degradation of PU matrices into isocyanate and alcohol along with a clear sign of process complexity [20]. As for T_{d1} and T_{d2} , they were related not only to hard-segment dissociation of PU/HNT nanocomposites [21], but also to a bond disentangle of water molecules in empty tubular lumens of HNTs [22]. T_{d3} and T_{d4} were referred to as the thermal decomposition of PU soft segments [23] and carbon degradation accordingly.

Four TGA peaks appeared for neat PU at the temperature ranges of 41-348°C, 348-387°C, 387-460°C and 663-788°C. Conversely, four temperature ranges were also identified at 28-358°C, 358-391°C, 391-465°C and 664-782°C with respect to four corresponding TGA peaks of PU/HNT nanocomposites reinforced with 2 wt% HNTs. The addition of HNTs to PU matrices increased T_{d1} , T_{d2} , T_{d3} and T_{d4} to higher temperature levels when compared with those of neat PU, as indicated in Fig. 6(b). This tendency could be caused by barrier effect of HNTs to postpone the dissociation of PU hard segments, resulting in the increase of T_d [23]. Moreover, an entrapping mechanism of HNT lumens for degradation products of polymers increased thermal stability and significantly delayed mass transport [24]. When HNT content was beyond 2 wt%, the decomposition temperatures of nanocomposite samples slightly decreased, in particular for T_{d3} and T_{d4} of PU/HNT nanocomposites at HNT contents of 4, 6, 8 and 10 wt% shown in Table 7. It might be ascribed to inhibited hydrogen bonding between hard segment domains of PU matrices and embedded HNTs to hinder the retention of thermal stability for polymer

nanocomposites [21]. Generally speaking, T_{d1} , T_{d2} , T_{d3} and T_{d4} of nanocomposite samples were higher than those of neat PU. It implied that the presence of HNTs within PU matrices tended to improve thermal stability of resulting PU/HNT nanocomposites.

Figure 6: TGA thermograms for PU and PU/HNT nanocomposites: (a) TGA curves and (b) DTG curves. Note T_d refers to the decomposition temperature.

Material type	Sample batch	T_{d1} (°C)	DTG (%/°C)	T_{d2} (°C)	DTG (%/°C)	T_{d3} (°C)	DTG (%/°C)	T_{d4} (°C)	DTG (%/°C)
Neat PU	PU	325.31	0.5661	371.19	0.5118	416.85	1.021	730.08	0.1732
2 wt% HNTs	NC-2 wt% HNT	337.59	0.6223	376.4	0.5418	417.49	1.017	730.15	0.1882
4 wt% HNTs	NC-4 wt% HNT	333.04	0.5336	373.41	0.5196	418.13	1.056	729.12	0.1873
6 wt% HNTs	NC-6 wt% HNT	327.52	0.3655	372.4	0.4496	424.3	0.9843	734.81	0.1563
8 wt% HNTs	NC-8 wt% HNT	326.49	0.393	375.97	0.4568	426.36	0.9878	730.2	0.163
10 wt% HNTs	NC-10 wt% HNT	325.82	0.3656	370.47	0.455	423.82	0.9619	737.3	0.1718

DTG stands for derivative thermogravimetry, which is a technique that plots the derivative of the TGA curve and represents the rate of mass change with respect to temperature or time.

Table 7: TGA data summary of PU and PU/HNT nanocomposite samples.

3.4 DSC thermal analysis

DSC thermograms for nanocomposite samples at various HNT contents were displayed in Fig. 7, while their thermal parameters were presented in Table 8. As mentioned earlier, PU molecules comprise hard and soft segments. T_g is connected to hard segments because of covalent bonding of NCO and OH groups to influence the mobility of polymeric chains [25]. The presence of HNTs may promote covalent bonding despite the limitation to chain mobility of PU molecules, resulting in the increase of T_g [26]. The addition of HNT content up to 4 wt% within PU matrices increased T_g to be 42.56°C, as opposed to 40.96°C for neat PU according to Fig. 7(a) and Table 8. When HNT content was increased, urethane stability was disturbed, inducing a further drop in T_g [21]. The incorporation of HNTs within PU matrices generated microphase separation due to specific transformation into hard segments by embedding such nanoparticles [26]. The addition of small amounts of HNTs at approximately 2 wt% in nanocomposites enhanced melting temperature up to 166.16°C when compared with that of neat PU at 161.32°C. Beyond this content level, the purification of soft segments prevailed, which was followed by the extraction of hard segments from the mixture. Accordingly, T_m shifted to the lower temperature level shown in Table 8, which was supported by previous work carried out by Razzaq et al. [27].

The inclusion of HNTs in nanocomposites yielded a higher χ_c owing to typical nucleating effect of HNTs [26]. When HNT content was increased to 6 wt%, χ_c of nanocomposite samples was improved by 55% relative to that of neat PU, as shown in Table 8. A further increase in HNT content from 6 to 10 wt% yielded a reduction in the growth rate of nuclei in the crystallisation process. It was evidenced by approximately 10% increase in χ_c . Additionally, the incorporation of HNTs also shifted DSC peaks with respect to the crystallisation temperatures of hard and soft segments, which were represented by $T_{c,HS}$ and $T_{c,SS}$, as demonstrated in Fig. 8(b) and Table 8. A higher T_c was proven to increase microphase separation, thus leading to pure soft segments and better shape fixity [26, 28].

Figure 7: DSC thermograms of nanocomposite samples at various HNT contents: (a) heating process and (b) cooling process.

Material type	Sample batch	T_g (°C)	$T_{c,SS}$ (°C)	$T_{c,HS}$ (°C)	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	ΔH_c (J/g)	χ_c (%)
Neat PU	PU	40.96	-31.05	47.66	161.32	4.34	0.37	2.84
2 wt% HNT	NC-2 wt% HNT	42.44	-30.12	48.44	166.16	4.26	0.34	2.85
4 wt% HNT	NC-4 wt% HNT	42.56	-29.88	49.36	163.32	5.18	0.64	3.38
6 wt% HNT	NC-6 wt% HNT	42.35	-28.56	49.43	163.04	6.23	0.43	4.41
8 wt% HNT	NC-8 wt% HNT	41.57	-28.07	48.42	164.03	6.43	0.49	4.61
10 wt% HNT	NC-10 wt% HNT	41.28	-27.24	48.04	161.78	6.68	0.53	4.89

ΔH_m and ΔH_c denote the heat of fusion and heat of crystallization of neat PU and PU/HNT nanocomposites respectively.

Table 8: DSC thermal properties for neat PU and PU/HNT nanocomposites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study presented holistic evaluation of HNT addition on NPR, shape memory behaviour and thermal stability of 3D printed PU/HNT nanocomposites. In general, the presence of HNTs in PU matrices could promote shape fixity ratio of PU/HNT nanocomposites despite slight drop in both shape recovery ratio and NPR, along with prolonged recovery time. The presence of 10 wt% HNTs within PU matrices improved shape fixity ratio of PU/HNT nanocomposites up to 12% though a slight decrease occurred in shape recovery ratio (9%) and NPR (60%), along with prolonged recovery time by 45%. They might have great commercial potential as a shape-memory shock absorber in the future.

The inclusion of HNTs enhanced thermal stability of PU/HNT nanocomposites, which was indicative of their relatively high decomposition temperatures. It could be associated with thermal barrier effect of HNTs to postpone the degradation of PU hard segments. Furthermore, an entrapping mechanism of HNT lumens played a significant role in increasing thermal stability of nanocomposite samples. Finally, the incorporation of HNTs also elevated T_g , T_m , T_c and χ_c due to much better covalent bonding, microphase separation and nucleating effect of HNTs in addition to evident mobility restriction of PU molecules.

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